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Consortium

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1 Introduction

One of the goals of the ASPECTS project was to develop techniques to infer entropy production with a fully suspended carbon nanotube (CNT) device. As planned, we have obtain bounds on the entropy production in this system. We have not exploited the quantum TURs obtained in T1.1 to obtain model-independent bounds on entropy production, as we have concentrated our efforts on the translation of the electrical signals obtained from our solid-state device at cryogenic temperatures into relevant thermodynamic quantities and on analyzing them within the framework of thermodynamics. Several challenges from a theoretical standpoint, such as the intricacies of non-equilibrium conditions, were overcome to complete this deliverable. This is the first demonstration of inference on thermodynamic quantities in a nanoelectromechanical system. The work presented in this report was completed by the ASPECTS consortium participants (Federico Fedele, Mark Mitchison and Natalia Ares) and other researchers at no cost to the project (Kushagra Aggarwal, Juliette Monsel, Joe Dunlop, Federico Cerisola, Jorge Tabanera, Lea Bresque, Sofia Sevitz, Janet Anders and Juan M.R. Parrondo).

2 The experiment

Figure 1: The experimental setup features a CNT device anchored at 50 mK. A cavity, composed of a surface-mount inductor and parasitic capacitance, is connected to the device’s source to enable probing of the mechanical motion. A SQUID amplifier, maintained at 50 mK, is followed by a HEMT amplifier at the 4 K stage. Various DC and fast lines are connected to the device, as illustrated in the figure.

A nanoelectromechanical resonator is formed by suspending a CNT over source and drain

metal electrodes. The electrostatic potential of the CNT is controlled using five gate electrodes with voltages: V_{G1} to V_{G5} . The current through the CNT, I_{DC} , is measured while applying a source-drain bias voltage V_{SD} . An rf drive is connected to the middle gate to excite the mechanical motion of the CNT, and the motion can be monitored using an rf tank circuit. The full experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. An electrical cavity is connected to one of the electrodes of the CNT. This connection allows probing the motion, wherein the electrical signal generated due to the mechanical motion is amplified by a series of amplifiers: a SQUID amplifier (Ref. [1]), a HEMT amplifier, and a room temperature amplifier. Finally, the amplified signal at room temperature is connected to a lock-in amplifier and measured using homodyne detection. The data is then collected by a PC as a digital record.

Figure 2: **a)** A CNT device suspended over two metal electrodes. An electrical cavity is connected to one of the contacts, and the electrical signal P_{out} is measured, as illustrated in Figure 1. **b)** Energy-space representation of the device. Due to strong coupling to the reservoirs, the energy level experiences lifetime broadening. **c)** The thermodynamic quantities involved in this system. The quantum dot energy level is the working fluid, where the mechanical oscillator can either perform or extract work W , and heat Q is exchanged with the Fermi reservoirs.

The energy space representation of the device is shown in Figure 2(b). The source and drain electrodes act as Fermi reservoirs with chemical potentials μ_S and μ_D , with their difference controlled experimentally using V_{SD} . The single electron energy level μ is strongly coupled to the two electrodes with tunneling rates Γ_S and Γ_D . In this regime ($\hbar\Gamma \gg k_B T$), the energy level experiences lifetime broadening, where T is the temperature of the system, and quantum tunneling noise dominates over thermal noise.

This system can be viewed as an equivalent of a nanomechanical piston and working fluid (see Figure 2(c)). The single energy level acts as a working fluid such that the mechanical motion of the CNT performs work W on the system while the Fermi reservoirs can exchange heat Q . Due to a finite V_{SD} and lifetime broadening in this system, this device operates away from equilibrium with no thermal reservoirs. This setup could allow the study of nanoscale devices subject to non-equilibrium conditions.

2.1 Transduction of displacement

Figure 3: **a)** When the CNT moves due to mechanical motion, the capacitance between the CNT and the gate electrode changes. This alteration causes the electrostatic potential experienced by the quantum dot to vary. **b)** For small enough oscillations, i.e., when the displacement is much smaller than the distance between the gate electrodes and the CNT, the effect of this change in capacitance can have the same effect as an oscillating gate voltage $V_G(t)$. This oscillation generates a current $I(t)$ through the CNT with the same frequency as that of the mechanical oscillator.

The mechanical motion results in a change of capacitance between the gate electrodes and the CNT. For small enough oscillations, this change in capacitance can be considered as an effective oscillating voltage, with the same frequency as that of the mechanical motion. The oscillating gate voltage modulates the quantum dot energy level, causing an oscillating current through the CNT.

We make the following assumptions for the transduction of mechanical motion into an electrical signal:

- The conductance is just a function of charge q on the CNT. Therefore, any instantaneous value of gate voltage V_G yields a specific instantaneous value of current, i.e., $q(t) \rightarrow V_G(t) \rightarrow I(t)$.
- The electron transport is much faster than the mechanical motion. This is generally true for our device as $\Gamma_{S,D} \gg \omega_m$.

We can now find the conductance for any particular instance of time

$$G(q(t)) \approx G(q_0) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial q} \delta q(t). \quad (1)$$

We can approximate the instantaneous charge as

$$\delta q(t) \approx \left(\frac{dq}{dV_G} \right)_z \delta V_G(t) + \left(\frac{\partial q}{\partial z} \right)_{V_G} \delta z(t). \quad (2)$$

The first term corresponds to the change in charge due to electrostatic effects, while the second term corresponds to the mechanical oscillations. For small enough changes, the first term is neglected. Also,

$$q = c_G V_G^{\text{DC}}, \quad (3)$$

and,

$$\delta q = c_G \delta V_G(t) + c'_G V_G^{\text{DC}} \delta z(t), \quad (4)$$

where c_G is the associated gate capacitance.

Ignoring the first term, as it is the electrostatic contribution, and substituting this in equation (1)

$$\delta G(t) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial q} c'_G V_G^{\text{DC}} \delta z(t), \quad (5)$$

$$\delta G(t) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial V_G} V_G^{\text{DC}} \frac{c'_G}{c_G} \delta z(t), \quad (6)$$

$$\delta I(t) = V_{\text{SD}} \delta G(t), \quad (7)$$

$$\delta I(t) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial V_G} V_G^{\text{DC}} V_{\text{SD}} \frac{c'_G}{c_G} \delta z(t). \quad (8)$$

We can estimate c'_G by assuming the CNT as a cylinder and the gates as an infinite plane, which yields

$$c'_G = \frac{c_G}{d \ln\left(\frac{2d}{r}\right)}, \quad (9)$$

where d is the separation between the gates and the CNT, and r is the radius of the CNT.

Finally,

$$V(t) = Z_{\text{trans}} I(t). \quad (10)$$

This $V(t)$ is amplified through the amplifier chain having an impedance Z_{trans} , and it is demodulated, giving us the final measured voltage.

2.2 Protocol

Using the gate voltages, the electrochemical potential can be controlled such that μ_N can be either empty (state 0) or full (state 1). Therefore, state 0 is achieved when $\mu_N > \mu_S, \mu_D$ and state 1 is achieved when $\mu_N < \mu_S, \mu_D$. However, within the bias window, where $\mu_D < \mu_N < \mu_S$, the quantum dot constantly transitions between State 0 and State 1 as electrons tunnel through. This can be regarded as a reset state in the context of information thermodynamics. As shown in Figure 4(a), μ_N can be positioned right at the edge of the bias window, and then the mechanical motion can be used to shift μ_N within this bias window, effectively erasing information as an indeterminate state (0 or 1) is reset to state 0. In this scenario, the mechanical oscillator is required to dissipate heat.

Figure 4(b) illustrates a control experiment. Here, μ_N is set above the source and drain electrochemical potentials, ensuring that the mechanical motion does not alter the state of the system. In this case, the mechanical oscillator is not expected to dissipate any heat.

The experimental protocol, as depicted in Figure 4(c), is performed as follows: First, the gate voltage is so that the quantum dot is set to the desired initial state, followed by an rf burst driving the mechanical oscillator. A brief wait period is introduced to eliminate any transients, after which the decaying signal resulting from the damping of the mechanical motion is measured. This process allows for the probing of the displacement, frequency, and dissipation of the mechanical oscillator, which will be utilized in subsequent sections to estimate the relevant thermodynamic quantities.

3 Electromechanical Model

In this section we formulate a model to capture the dynamics of the device and estimate how the relevant thermodynamic quantities can be estimated from experimental data.

Figure 4: **a)** The occupation of the quantum dot can be controlled by changing the position of the energy level μ_N relative to the source and drain electrochemical potentials. In the case of the information reset of the protocol, the μ_N is placed such that the mechanical oscillations move the μ_N inside the bias window, effectively changing the quantum dot from State 0 to a reset state. **b)** A control protocol, during which no information is reset, can be implemented when the μ_N is significantly above the source and drain electrochemical potentials. **c)** The experimental protocol is implemented in four steps: setting the gate voltage, driving the mechanical oscillator, waiting for a predetermined period, and then measuring the electrical signal from the cavity.

3.1 Equation of motion

We use the same approach as in Ref. [2], but for the gate and bias voltages considered in this experiment, we need to take into account both the energy dependence of the tunnel barriers and the change in the stiffness of the nanotube with gate voltage. First, due to the energy-dependent tunnel barriers, the quantum dot exchanges electrons with the lead $\nu = S, D$ at rates (in the lifetime broadened regime $\hbar\Gamma_b \gg k_B T$)

$$\gamma_\nu^{\text{in}}(\mu) = \gamma_\nu(\mu)\rho_\nu(\mu), \quad \gamma_\nu^{\text{out}}(\mu) = \gamma_\nu(\mu)(1 - \rho_\nu(\mu)). \quad (11)$$

with [3]

$$\gamma_\nu(\mu) = \Gamma_\nu e^{b_\nu(\mu - \mu_\nu)}, \quad \rho_\nu(\mu) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \arctan\left(\frac{2(\mu_\nu - \mu)}{\hbar\Gamma_b}\right), \quad (12)$$

and $\Gamma_b = \gamma_S + \gamma_D$. The values of the coefficients Γ_ν and b_ν are extracted from the experimental data by fitting the Coulomb peaks. The electrochemical potential of the quantum dot depends on the mechanical displacement z as [2]

$$\mu(z) = \mu_0(V_G) + \hbar\gamma_m \frac{z}{z_{\text{pm}}}, \quad (13)$$

where $\mu_0(V_G) = \alpha(V_0 - V_G)$ is the electrochemical potential of the dot at $z = 0$, with α the lever arm and V_0 an offset on the gate voltage.

We consider the regime

$$\gamma_{\text{LR}}(\mu) \gg \omega_m, \quad \gamma_m \gg \Gamma_m, \quad (14)$$

Therefore, we can use the adiabatic approximation and consider that, on the timescale of the mechanical evolution, the dot's population is always the equilibrium population,

$$p(z) = \frac{\gamma_S^{\text{in}}(\mu(z)) + \gamma_D^{\text{in}}(\mu(z))}{\gamma_t(\mu(z))}, \quad (15)$$

with $\gamma_t = \gamma_S + \gamma_D$. The evolution of the mechanics is thus given by

$$\ddot{z} + \Gamma_m \dot{z} + \omega_m(V_G)^2 z = -p(z)\gamma_m\omega_m(V_G)z_{\text{pm}}. \quad (16)$$

$\omega_m(V_G)$ is the mechanical resonance frequency when p is constant, accounting for the effects of the gate voltage on the overall stiffness of the nanotube. Furthermore, the change in ω_m with V_G is relatively small compared to the frequency softening due to the electromechanical coupling described in Ref. [2], therefore we can carry on with the same procedure, assuming that γ_m can be considered as constant within the range of the gate voltage sweep. Neglecting the mechanical damping when looking at only a few oscillations, the mechanical equation of motion reads

$$\ddot{z} + \omega_m^2 \left[z + 2p(\mu(z)) \frac{\gamma_m}{\omega_m} \right] = 0. \quad (17)$$

The change in ω_m with V_G is due to electrostatic effects and therefore $\omega_m(V_G)$ depends on the average number of charges in the dot. Applying the linear model from Ref. [4] does not work so well here. This is because we are operating at large bias and thus cannot approximate the dot population with a single step in the middle of the bias window. We instead approximated $\omega_m(V_G)$ as a linear function of population, $\omega_m(V_G) = ap(\mu_0(V_G)) + b$, where p is the dot population, see Equation (15), at the electrochemical potential $\mu_0(V_G)$ (i.e., for $z = 0$). We obtain the coefficients a and b by fitting V_{demod} as a function of driving frequency f_{ex} and gate voltage V_{G1} , see yellow dashed line in Figure 5.

3.2 Effective mechanical frequency

Under the approximation of small displacements, the effective resonance frequency ω_{eff} can be estimated from Equation (17) by linearizing $p(\mu)$ around μ_0 ,

$$p(\mu) = p(\mu_0) + (\mu - \mu_0) \left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu_0}. \quad (18)$$

From Ref. [2], we obtain

$$\omega_{\text{eff}}(V_G) = \sqrt{\omega_m(V_G)^2 + 2\gamma_m^2 \hbar \omega_m(V_G) \left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu_0(V_G)}}, \quad (19)$$

but the expression of $\left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu_0}$ is more complicated than in Ref. [2] due to energy dependence of the tunnel barriers,

$$\left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} = \frac{1}{\gamma_t} \left(\gamma_D \left. \frac{\partial \rho_D}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} + \gamma_S \left. \frac{\partial \rho_S}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} \right) + \frac{1}{\gamma_t^2} (\rho_D - \rho_S) \left(\gamma_S \left. \frac{\partial \gamma_D}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} - \gamma_D \left. \frac{\partial \gamma_S}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} \right), \quad (20)$$

with

$$\left. \frac{\partial \gamma_{\nu}}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} = b_{\nu} \gamma_{\nu}, \quad \left. \frac{\partial \rho_{\nu}}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu} = \frac{-2}{\pi \hbar \Gamma_b} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{2(\mu_{\nu} - \mu)}{\hbar \Gamma_b} \right)^2}. \quad (21)$$

$\omega_{\text{eff}}(V_G)$ in the small amplitude limit is plotted in Figure fig:wm(Vg)b (dash-dotted pink line) using the tunnel rates obtained from fitting the Coulomb peak from Figure fig:wm(Vg)a. We observe that the dip around μ_D is almost nonexistent, unlike in the data, suggesting that we have overestimated the asymmetry between γ_D and γ_S , while the dip around μ_S is deeper than the data, suggesting that the small amplitude limit does not fully apply in the experiment. This leads to a shallower and broader dip due to the large amplitude of the mechanical motion. We finally confirm that the experiment is beyond the small amplitude limit by numerically integrating the equation of motion Equation (17) for the amplitudes Δz corresponding to the maximum amplitude in Figure 5(b) for each gate voltage (solid yellow curve in Figure 5(a)).

3.3 Numerical simulations of the driven mechanical motion

We cannot solve the equation of motion Equation (16) analytically, so we integrate it numerically for different drive frequencies f_{ex} . The amplitude of the mechanical motion in the driven steady state is plotted in Figure 6. We clearly observe a softening of the mechanical frequency around the electrochemical potentials of both reservoirs. This softening corresponds to regions where the dot population p varies significantly with z . Additionally, we note that the amplitude reached for a similar driving strength is smaller in these regions, which corresponds to a decrease in the mechanical quality factor due to extra mechanical damping caused by electronic transport.

4 Thermodynamics of the system

4.1 Thermodynamic quantities

We define the basic thermodynamic quantities from our model of the dot and derive an expression of the Landauer principle. In this section, we approximate the dot evolution using the master equation

$$\dot{p} = \gamma^{\text{in}}(\mu(z))(1-p) - \gamma^{\text{out}}(\mu(z))p. \quad (22)$$

The population exchange with each of the source and drain electrodes is given by the probability currents

$$j_{S,D} = \gamma_{S,D}^{\text{in}}(\mu(z))(1-p) - \gamma_{S,D}^{\text{out}}(\mu(z))p, \quad (23)$$

such that $\dot{p} = j_S + j_D$.

The instantaneous average internal energy of the dot is given by

$$U(t) = \mu(z)p, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\mu(t) = \mu_0 + \hbar\gamma_m \frac{z(t)}{z_{\text{pm}}}. \quad (25)$$

Taking the time derivative, we obtain $\dot{U} = \dot{\mu}p + \mu\dot{p}$. The first part corresponds to the mechanical work,

$$\dot{W} = \dot{\mu}(t)p(t), \quad (26)$$

meanwhile, the second term must be rewritten as $\mu\dot{p} = (\mu - \mu_S)j_S + (\mu - \mu_D)j_D + \mu_S j_S + \mu_D j_D$. The chemical work done by the electrons is $\dot{W}_{\text{ch}} = \mu_S j_S + \mu_D j_D$. The heat exchange with each lead is

$$\beta\dot{Q}_\nu = \beta(\mu - \mu_\nu)j_\nu = -j_\nu \log\left(\frac{\gamma_\nu^{\text{in}}}{\gamma_\nu^{\text{out}}}\right), \quad (27)$$

with $\nu = S, D$. In this definition, we call $\gamma^{\text{in/out}} = \gamma_S^{\text{in/out}} + \gamma_D^{\text{in/out}}$ and the detailed balance property of the electron leads $\log(\gamma_\nu^{\text{in}}/\gamma_\nu^{\text{out}}) = -\beta(\mu - \mu_\nu)$. To recover the second principle of thermodynamics, we consider the Shannon entropy of the dot $S = -p \log p - (1-p) \log(1-p)$ whose time derivative is

$$\dot{S} = -(j_S + j_D) \log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right). \quad (28)$$

Then, the total entropy production is

$$\dot{\Sigma} = \dot{S} - \beta\dot{Q} = -j_S \log\left(\frac{p\gamma_S^{\text{out}}}{(1-p)\gamma_S^{\text{in}}}\right) - j_D \log\left(\frac{p\gamma_D^{\text{out}}}{(1-p)\gamma_D^{\text{in}}}\right) \geq 0. \quad (29)$$

Their positivity comes from the definition of j_ν . $\dot{Q} = \dot{Q}_S + \dot{Q}_D$ is the total heat flow from the source to drain reservoir.

4.2 Landauer interpretation

We compute the work during the information reset in Figure 4, that is the first half of the mechanical period, starting at $t = 0$ at the minimum position (with $z(0) < 0$) and ending at the maximum position at $t = \frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}}$. In the adiabatic approximation:

$$W = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}}} dt \dot{\mu}(t)p(\mu(z(t))) = \int_{\mu_i}^{\mu_f} d\mu p(\mu) \quad (30)$$

with

$$\mu_i = \mu_0 + \hbar\gamma_m \frac{z(0)}{z_{\text{pm}}}, \quad \mu_f = \mu_0 + \hbar\gamma_m \frac{z(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}})}{z_{\text{pm}}} \quad (31)$$

where $z(0)$ is taken to be a minimum and $z(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}})$ a maximum of the displacement.

If we assume the initial and final values of the occupation $p(0) \sim \frac{1}{2}$ and $p(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}}) \sim 0$, the total Shannon entropy change is just $\Delta S = -\log 2$. The heat exchange is

$$\Delta Q = \Delta U - W - W_{\text{ch}}. \quad (32)$$

As $U(t) = \mu(t)p$, we obtain $\Delta U = \frac{\mu_i}{2}$. In terms of the work, the second principle is

$$W + W_{\text{ch}} \geq k_B T \log 2 + \frac{\mu_i}{2}. \quad (33)$$

Now, we can introduce the adiabatic approximation to evaluate W .

4.2.1 Energy independent tunnel barriers and no broadening of the dot level

Here we neglect the tunnel barrier energy dependence and the width of the dot level. As above, we consider that the electrodes are at zero temperature:

$$\gamma_\nu^{\text{in}}(\mu) = \Gamma_\nu \Theta(\mu_\nu - \mu), \quad \gamma_\nu^{\text{out}}(\mu) = \Gamma_\nu (1 - \Theta(\mu_\nu - \mu)). \quad (34)$$

We compute the work during the information reset in Figure 4, that is the first half of the mechanical period, starting at $t = 0$ at the minimum position (with $z(0) < 0$) and ending at the maximum position at $t = \frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}}$, in the adiabatic approximation, $W = \int_{\mu_i}^{\mu_f} d\mu p(\mu)$.

In the case where $\mu_0 = \mu_S$ and a large enough bias is considered such that $\mu_i > \mu_D$, we have

$$p(\mu_i) = \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b}, \quad p(\mu_f) = 0, \quad (35)$$

$$\gamma_S^{\text{in}}(\mu_i) = \gamma_S, \quad \gamma_S^{\text{in}}(\mu_f) = 0. \quad (36)$$

Therefore,

$$W = \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b} (\mu_S - \mu_i) = \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b} \hbar \gamma_m \frac{|z(0)|}{z_{\text{pm}}}. \quad (37)$$

Since the dot level is not broadened, we can make the work cost W arbitrarily small since any $\mu_f > \mu_S$ is enough to get $p = 0$. This is consistent with Landauer's principle since $k_B T \log 2 \xrightarrow{T \rightarrow 0} 0$.

If instead we take $\mu_0 = \mu_D$, then the Landauer erasure would correspond to the downward motion of the mechanics (with $z(0)$ maximum and $z(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}})$ minimum) since we would go from $0 < p = \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b} < 1$ to $p = 1$. In that case,

$$W = \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b} (\mu_D - \mu_i) + \mu_f - \mu_D = \hbar \gamma_m \left(-\frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b} \frac{z(0)}{z_{\text{pm}}} + \frac{z(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}})}{z_{\text{pm}}} \right) < 0. \quad (38)$$

4.2.2 Level broadening of the dot

Here we neglect the tunnel barrier energy dependence to simplify the calculation and interpretation but take into account the broadening of the dot level. We compute the work for the information reset in Figure 4, that is the first half of the mechanical period, starting at $t = 0$ at the minimum position (with $z(0) < 0$) and ending at the maximum position at $t = \frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}}$. In the adiabatic approximation:

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \int_{\mu_i}^{\mu_f} d\mu p(\mu) \\ &= \mu_f p(\mu_f) - \mu_i p(\mu_i) + \sum_{\nu=S,D} \mu_\nu \frac{\gamma_\nu^{\text{in}}(\mu_i) - \gamma_\nu^{\text{in}}(\mu_f)}{\Gamma_b} \\ &\quad + \sum_{\nu=S,D} \frac{\hbar \Gamma_\nu}{4\pi} \log \left(\frac{(\hbar \Gamma_b)^2 + 4(\mu_\nu - \mu_f)^2}{(\hbar \Gamma_b)^2 + 4(\mu_\nu - \mu_i)^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where $z(0)$ is taken to be a minimum and $z(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}})$ a maximum of the displacement. This expression (39) should in principle be computable from the amplitude of the motion we extract from Figure 5 (see Section 2.1) since it can be expressed in terms of the mechanical amplitude by using Equation (31).

In the case when $\mu_0 \gg \mu_S, \hbar \Gamma_b$, the work is

$$W \simeq \frac{\hbar \Gamma_b}{2\pi} \frac{\Delta\mu}{\mu_0} \xrightarrow{\mu_0 \rightarrow \infty} 0. \quad (40)$$

In the case when $\mu_0 = \mu_S$ and we have taken a large enough bias to neglect the contribution from the drain,

$$p(\mu_i) \simeq \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b}, \quad p(\mu_f) \simeq 0, \quad (41)$$

$$\gamma_S^{\text{in}}(\mu_i) \simeq \gamma_S, \quad \gamma_S^{\text{in}}(\mu_f) \simeq 0. \quad (42)$$

Therefore,

$$W \simeq \hbar \gamma_{\text{m}} \frac{|z(0)|}{z_{\text{pm}}} \frac{\gamma_S}{\Gamma_b} + \frac{\hbar \Gamma_S}{2\pi} \log \left(\left| \frac{z(\frac{\pi}{\omega_{\text{eff}}})}{z(0)} \right| \right). \quad (43)$$

Note that unlike in the previous case, we cannot make this work cost arbitrarily small since to get $p(\mu_f) \simeq 0$, we need to have $\mu - \mu_S \gg \hbar \Gamma_b$. This constraint gives us a minimal mechanical amplitude which in turn gives a minimum work cost.

5 Erasure with two fermion baths

In the previous section, we explored how to extract thermodynamic quantities from experimental data. However, a pertinent question arises: what is the fundamental bound on the cost of information erasure in this scenario? Given the presence of Fermi reservoirs and the strong coupling of the quantum dot, quantum tunneling noise dominates over thermal noise. This indicates that we are operating under non-equilibrium conditions with athermal baths. In this section, we develop the theory for a generalized version of Landauer's principle, particularly tailored for fermion baths.

5.1 Average cyclic work cost of bit reset

We consider a quantum dot with an energy level μ , and suppose that the steady-state occupation probability varies as some function $n(\mu)$. Suppose that we can vary μ as a control parameter: the work cost of quasistatically transforming the configuration $(\mu_i, n(\mu_i)) \mapsto (\mu_f, n(\mu_f))$ is given by:

$$W = \int_{\mu_i}^{\mu_f} n(\mu) d\mu. \quad (44)$$

However, this leaves the value of μ changed. A *cycle* for transforming the occupation state takes the configuration $(\mu_i, n(\mu_i)) \mapsto (\mu_i, n(\mu_f))$, with the energy level restored to its initial value. This can be achieved reversibly by *very quickly* resetting $\mu_f \mapsto \mu_i$ after the quasistatic step, fast enough that the state evolution is negligible and occupation remains at $n(\mu_f)$. This reset step incurs an extra work cost $\int_{\mu_f}^{\mu_i} n(\mu_f) d\mu$, so that the work for the cycle is given by:

$$W = \int_{\mu_i}^{\mu_f} n(\mu) - n(\mu_f) d\mu. \quad (45)$$

A case of particular interest is a cycle where the initial configuration is $(\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}, n = \frac{1}{2})$, and where the final configuration is either $(\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}, n = 0)$ or $(\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}, n = 1)$, with $\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}$ being the value of the dot's energy level for which the steady state occupation $n(\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}) = \frac{1}{2}$. If the occupation is taken to represent a bit of information, these processes represent a Landauer-like reset to a definite state, respectively 0 or 1 for the two cycles. Assume that $n(\mu)$ is monotone-decreasing, with $\lim_{\mu \rightarrow \infty} n(\mu) = 0$ and $\lim_{\mu \rightarrow -\infty} n(\mu) = 1$. The work cost W^0 of our reset-to-zero cycle is then given by (45) in the limit where $\mu_f \rightarrow \infty$:

$$W^0 = \int_{\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}}^{\infty} n(\mu) d\mu, \quad (46)$$

noting that $n(\mu_f)$ vanishes. Likewise, the work cost W^1 of the reset-to-one cycle is given by taking $\mu_f \rightarrow -\infty$ and $n(\mu_f) \rightarrow 1$:

$$W^1 = \int_{-\infty}^{\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}} 1 - n(\mu) d\mu, \quad (47)$$

In general, W^0 and W^1 may differ from each other, depending on the form of $n(\mu)$. In the context of information processing, 1s are required just as frequently as 0s for efficient coding. A fair measure of the cost of state reset is the *average* cyclic work cost of preparing either the empty state or the full occupancy state. Averaging eliminates any change in the system's internal energy¹, meaning that the work cost is solely associated with the entropic change. The quantity of interest is,

$$\bar{W} = \frac{1}{2} (W^0 + W^1). \quad (48)$$

5.2 Work is related to the spread of the occupation distribution

Our assumptions about $n(\mu)$ mean that $n'(\mu) = -\frac{dn}{d\mu}$ meets the definition of a probability density function, and $\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}$ represents the median of that distribution. Using integration by parts, the average work cost can be rewritten as [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}}^{\infty} n(\mu) d\mu + \int_{-\infty}^{\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}} 1 - n(\mu) d\mu \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \mu - \mu_{\frac{1}{2}} \right| \left(-\frac{dn}{d\mu} \right) d\mu. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The final integral in the above can be recognised as the *mean absolute deviation* of $n'(\mu)$, a measure of spread defined by $D(n') = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \mu - \mu_{\frac{1}{2}} \right| n'(\mu) d\mu$. The average work cost is directly related to the spread:

$$\bar{W} = \frac{1}{2} D(n'). \quad (50)$$

$n(\mu)$ need not be a canonical equilibrium distribution: it might instead represent a dynamical steady state for a dot in contact with multiple baths with different temperatures and chemical potentials. In that case, Equation (50) still applies, but may not reduce to the standard Landauer bound.

Incidentally, Equation (50) implies that the average cost of erasure from $n = \frac{1}{2}$ is always lower than for any other initial occupation, since the median is the point about which the mean absolute deviation is minimised.

5.3 Erasure with two Fermion baths

We consider a charge qubit encoded in a quantum dot which simultaneously interacts with two reservoirs with energy distributions $f_S(\epsilon)$ and $f_D(\epsilon)$ to calculate the cost of erasure with two Fermion baths. Take the reservoirs to be described by Fermi-Dirac distributions, $f_S(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\beta_S(\epsilon - \mu_S))}$ and $f_D(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\beta_D(\epsilon - \mu_D))}$, where $\mu_S \geq \mu_D$. Suppose, that the dot exchanges electrons with the source reservoir at rate Γ_S and with the drain reservoir at rate Γ_D . The tunneling rates are taken to be energy-independent. Let the dot have an unoccupied state with energy 0 and an occupied state with energy ϵ , with an occupation probability $p(\epsilon)$ (we will later

¹The final configuration is either $(\mu = \mu_{\frac{1}{2}}, p = 0)$ or $(\mu = \mu_{\frac{1}{2}}, p = 1)$, so on average the internal energy is $\frac{1}{2}\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}$.

account for broadening of the energy level). Let us take the particle currents in and out of the dot to be the following:

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_S^{\text{in}} &= \Gamma_S f_S(\epsilon) (1 - p(\epsilon)), & \gamma_S^{\text{out}} &= \Gamma_S (1 - f_S(\epsilon)) p(\epsilon), \\ \gamma_D^{\text{in}} &= \Gamma_D f_D(\epsilon) (1 - p(\epsilon)), & \gamma_D^{\text{out}} &= \Gamma_D (1 - f_D(\epsilon)) p(\epsilon).\end{aligned}\quad (51)$$

The steady-state occupation is achieved when the total currents in and out are balanced:

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_S^{\text{in}} + \gamma_D^{\text{in}} &= \gamma_S^{\text{out}} + \gamma_D^{\text{out}} \\ \implies p(\epsilon) &= \frac{\Gamma_S}{\Gamma_S + \Gamma_D} f_S(\epsilon) + \frac{\Gamma_D}{\Gamma_S + \Gamma_D} f_D(\epsilon).\end{aligned}\quad (52)$$

Let us denote the *relative* tunneling rates $G_S = \frac{\Gamma_S}{\Gamma_S + \Gamma_D}$ and $G_D = \frac{\Gamma_D}{\Gamma_S + \Gamma_D}$, noting $G_S + G_D = 1$.

5.3.1 Lifetime broadening

The energy level of the quantum dot is subject to lifetime broadening. In this case the control parameter μ does not represent the exact energy level, but instead the mean value of a probabilistic distribution of energies $g(\epsilon, \mu)$. Let us assume that the distribution does not change shape depending on μ but is only shifted; then we can write it as $g(\epsilon - \mu)$. If the occupation of an exact energy level ϵ is described by $p(\epsilon)$, then the occupation as a function of μ is given by the cross-correlation,

$$n(\mu) = g \star p(\mu) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(\epsilon - \mu) p(\epsilon) d\epsilon. \quad (53)$$

Using standard properties of cross-correlation, the probability density function is $n'(\mu) = g \star p'(\mu)$, where $p'(\epsilon) = -\frac{dp}{d\epsilon}$. Therefore we can relate the average work cost of to the mean absolute deviation of the cross-correlation:

$$\overline{W} = \frac{1}{2} D(g \star p'). \quad (54)$$

5.4 Bounding the work cost of erasure

Given values of the electrochemical potential, temperature and tunnelling rate for each reservoir, it is straightforward to numerically evaluate \overline{W} using the above model; but there is no closed analytical expression. In fact it is difficult even to invert $n(\mu)$ to obtain a formula for $\mu_{\frac{1}{2}}$. However, it is possible to place analytic *bounds* on \overline{W} , and thereby analyse the relevant energy scales and their interplay. We will refer to general properties of the mean absolute deviation established in lemmas 1 and 2 (see the following section). Combining equations (53) and (54), it can be seen that:

$$\overline{W} = \frac{1}{2} D(g \star (G_S f'_S + G_D f'_D)), \quad (55)$$

where $f'_\nu(\epsilon) = -\frac{d}{d\mu} f_\nu(\epsilon)$, for $\nu = S, D$; which can be explicitly written as:

$$f'_\nu(\epsilon) = \frac{\beta_\nu e^{\beta_\nu(\epsilon - \mu_\nu)}}{(1 + e^{\beta_\nu(\epsilon - \mu_\nu)})^2}. \quad (56)$$

f'_ν defines a probability density function with median equal to the electrochemical potential μ_ν . The mean absolute deviation is given by:

$$D(f'_\nu) = \frac{2 \ln 2}{\beta_\nu}. \quad (57)$$

Returning to (55), we can apply lemmas 1(i) followed by 2(i), using the fact that that $f'_\nu(\mu_\nu + \epsilon) = f'_\nu(\mu_\nu - \epsilon)$ for all ϵ :

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{W} &\geq \frac{1}{2} \max \{D(g), D(G_S f'_S + G_D f'_D)\} \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2} \max \{D(g), G_S D(f'_S) + G_D D(f'_D), \min\{G_S, G_D\}(\mu_S - \mu_D)\} \\
&= \max \left\{ \frac{1}{2} D(g), \left(\frac{G_S}{\beta_S} + \frac{G_D}{\beta_D} \right) \ln 2, \frac{1}{2} \min\{G_S, G_D\}(\mu_S - \mu_D) \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

In the above, we have effectively identified three independent energy scales which contribute to the work cost of erasure. Let us denote them as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{therm}} &= \left(\frac{G_S}{\beta_S} + \frac{G_D}{\beta_D} \right) \ln 2 \\
E_{\text{bias}} &= \frac{1}{2} \min\{G_S, G_D\}(\mu_S - \mu_D) \\
E_{\text{broad}} &= \frac{1}{2} D(g).
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

E_{therm} relates to thermal broadening, and has the familiar form of the Landauer energy cost $k_B T \ln 2$, albeit with the temperature replaced by an average of the two reservoir temperatures weighted by the relative tunnelling rates. E_{bias} relates to the potential bias between source and drain reservoirs: the larger the bias, the larger the cost of erasure - although the effect is mitigated when the tunneling rate from one reservoir dominates the other (in that limit we effectively recover the single bath case). Finally, E_{broad} relates to the broadening of the dot's energy level, and will typically be of the order $\hbar \Gamma_{\text{tot}}$, where the total tunneling rate $\Gamma_{\text{tot}} = \Gamma_S + \Gamma_D$ quantifies the reciprocal of the typical time spent before tunneling out of the dot.

Note that Equation (58) is not a tight bound: aside from a few limiting cases it cannot be saturated, and so far we cannot rule out that in fact an optimal erasure protocol would require much *more* work than the right hand side of Equation (58) suggests. However, applying lemmas 1(ii) and 2(ii) to Equation (55), we can upper-bound the minimum work cost:

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{W} &\leq \frac{1}{2} \left(D(g) + D(G_S f'_S + G_D f'_D) \right) \\
&\leq \frac{1}{2} \left(D(g) + G_S D(f'_S) + G_D D(f'_D) + \min\{G_S, G_D\}(\mu_S - \mu_D) \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} D(g) + \left(\frac{G_S}{\beta_S} + \frac{G_D}{\beta_D} \right) \ln 2 + \frac{1}{2} \min\{G_S, G_D\}(\mu_S - \mu_D).
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

Putting this together with (58), we have:

$$\max \{E_{\text{therm}}, E_{\text{bias}}, E_{\text{broad}}\} \leq \bar{W} \leq E_{\text{therm}} + E_{\text{bias}} + E_{\text{broad}}. \tag{61}$$

Recall that \bar{W} is the average cost of preparing a 0 or 1 state using an ideal, thermodynamically reversible process. If the erasure were carried out in an inefficient manner, there is certainly nothing preventing the cost from exceeding $E_{\text{therm}} + E_{\text{bias}} + E_{\text{broad}}$: but in principle it is possible to do better.

Equation (61) tells that if any one of the three energy scales dominates the other two, it essentially solely determines the cost of erasure. For example if the source-drain bias were very much larger than the thermal energy and lifetime broadening, then we would have $E_{\text{bias}} \gg E_{\text{therm}}, E_{\text{broad}}$, and therefore $\bar{W} \approx E_{\text{bias}}$. Conversely, if any one of the energy scales is much smaller than the other two, then it is functionally irrelevant to the cost of erasure.

5.5 Bounds on the mean absolute deviation

Lemma 1. Let f and g be probability density functions. Then the mean absolute deviation D of the cross-correlation function $f \star g$ is bounded by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad & D(f \star g) \geq \max\{D(f), D(g)\} \\ \text{(ii)} \quad & D(f \star g) \leq D(f) + D(g). \end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

Proof. Recall $f \star g = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y)g(y-x)dy = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y+x)g(y)dy$. For the lower bound, (i), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} D(f \star g) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - m_{fg}| \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y+x)g(y)dy \right) dx \\ &= \int \left(\int |x - m_{fg}| f(y+x)dx \right) g(y)dy \\ &\geq \int D(f)g(y)dy \\ &= D(f). \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

Since $f \star g(x) = g \star f(-x)$, and since the mean absolute deviation of a function $h(x)$ is equal to that of $h(-x)$, then by the above reasoning we also have $D(f \star g) \geq D(g)$, which completes the proof of (i). On the other hand to show the upper bound,

$$\begin{aligned} D(f \star g) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |u - m_{fg}| f \star g(u)du \\ &\leq \int |u - (m_f - m_g)| f \star g(u)du \\ &= \int |u - (m_f - m_g)| \left(\int f(u+y)g(y)dy \right) du \\ &= \int \left(\int |u - (m_f - m_g)| f(u+y)du \right) g(y)dy \\ &= \int \left(\int |x - y - (m_f - m_g)| f(x)dx \right) g(y)dy \\ &\leq \iint (|x - m_f| + |y - m_g|) f(x)g(y)dx dy \\ &= \int \left(\int |x - m_f| f(x)dx \right) g(y)dy + \int \left(\int |y - m_g| g(y)dy \right) f(x)dx \\ &= \int D(f)g(y)dy + \int D(g)f(x)dx \\ &= D(f) + D(g) \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

In the fifth line we used the substitution $x = u + y$. This completes the proof of (ii).

Lemma 2. Let f be a probability density function which is even about its median m_f , such that for all x , $f(m_f + x) = f(m_f - x)$. Similarly, let g be a probability density function which is even about its median m_g , where $m_g \leq m_f$. Let p_f and p_g be probabilities such that $p_f + p_g = 1$. Then the mean absolute deviation of the convex sum $p_f f + p_g g$ is bounded by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad & D(p_f f + p_g g) \geq \max \left\{ p_f D(\mu_f) + p_g D(\mu_g), \min\{p_f, p_g\}(m_f - m_g) \right\} \\ \text{(ii)} \quad & D(p_f f + p_g g) \leq p_f D(\mu_f) + p_g D(\mu_g) + \min\{p_f, p_g\}(m_f - m_g). \end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

Proof. Let us denote $h(x) = p_f f(x) + p_g g(x)$; note that h is also a probability density function and its median $m_h \in [m_g, m_f]$. We will use the fact that the median minimises the

mean absolute deviation, in that for all a , $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - a|f(x)dx \geq \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - m_f|f(x)dx$. Then the mean absolute deviation of h is bounded as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
D(h) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - m_h|(p_f f(x) + p_g g(x))dx \\
&= p_f \int |x - m_h|f(x)dx + p_g \int |x - m_h|g(x)dx \\
&\geq p_f \int |x - m_f|f(x)dx + p_g \int |x - m_g|g(x)dx \\
&= p_f D(f) + p_g D(g).
\end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

On the other hand, we also have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - m_h|f(x)dx &= \int_{-\infty}^{m_f} (x - m_h)f(x)dx + \int_{m_f}^{\infty} (x - m_h)f(x)dx \\
&\quad + 2 \int_{-\infty}^{m_h} |x - m_h|f(x)dx \\
&= \int_0^{\infty} (m_f - u - m_h)f(m_f - u)du \\
&\quad + \int_0^{\infty} (m_f + u - m_h)f(m_f + u)du \\
&\quad + 2 \int_{-\infty}^{m_h} |x - m_h|f(x)dx \\
&= 2(m_f - m_h) \int_0^{\infty} f(m_f + u)du \\
&\quad + 2 \int_{-\infty}^{m_h} |x - m_h|f(x)dx \\
&= m_f - m_h + 2 \int_{-\infty}^{m_h} |x - m_h|f(x)dx.
\end{aligned} \tag{67}$$

We have used that $f(m_f + x) = f(m_f - x)$. In the final line we used that $\int_{m_f}^{\infty} f(x)dx = \frac{1}{2}$, by definition of the median. By a similar argument for g ,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - m_h|g(x)dx = m_h - m_g + 2 \int_{m_h}^{\infty} |x - m_h|g(x)dx. \tag{68}$$

Combining (67) and (68):

$$\begin{aligned}
D(h) &= p_f(m_f - m_h) + p_g(m_h - m_g) \\
&\quad + 2 \left(p_f \int_{-\infty}^{m_h} |x - m_h|f(x)dx \right. \\
&\quad \left. + p_g \int_{m_h}^{\infty} |x - m_h|g(x)dx \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{69}$$

Since the integral terms are always positive, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned}
D(h) &\geq p_f(m_f - m_h) + p_g(m_h - m_g) \\
&\geq \min\{p_f, p_g\}(m_f - m_g).
\end{aligned} \tag{70}$$

Taking inequalities (66) and (70) together, the claim (i) follows.

Moreover, since $D(h) = \min_m \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x - m| h(x) dx$, then from (69) we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
D(h) &= \min_m \left\{ p_f(m_f - m) + p_g(m - m_g) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2 \left(p_f \int_{-\infty}^m |x - m| f(x) dx \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + p_g \int_m^{\infty} |x - m| g(x) dx \right) \right\} \\
&\leq p_f(m_f - m_g) + p_g(m_g - m_g) \\
&\quad + 2p_f \int_{-\infty}^{m_g} |x - m_g| f(x) dx \\
&\quad + 2p_g \int_{m_g}^{\infty} |x - m_g| g(x) dx \\
&= p_f(m_f - m_g) + p_g D(g) \\
&\quad + 2p_f \int_{-\infty}^{m_g} |x - m_g| f(x) dx \\
&= p_f(m_f - m_g) + p_g D(g) \\
&\quad + 2p_f \int_{-\infty}^{m_f} |x - m_f| f(x) dx \\
&= p_f(m_f - m_g) + p_g D(g) + p_f D(f).
\end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

We have used the fact that $m_f \geq m_g$, and in the final line we used the assumption that f is even about m_f . If we instead take $m = m_f$, then by the same arguments,

$$D(h) \leq p_g(m_f - m_g) + p_g D(g) + p_f D(f). \tag{72}$$

Combining (71) and (72), we certainly have $D(h) \leq \min\{p_f, p_g\}(m_f - m_g) + p_f D(f) + p_g D(g)$, which was the claimed bound (ii).

6 Quantifying energy dissipation

We have methods to estimate the work done in changing the occupation state of the quantum dot, and we believe that this work is done *almost* reversibly, since the tunneling rates are much faster than the mechanical frequency, meaning that the process is effectively quasistatic. However, it strengthens our argument if we have an empirical way to quantify the energy dissipated in changing the occupation of the dot – which we expect to be a small fraction of the work done.

In the oscillator-dot system, there is periodic conversion of kinetic energy into a combination of elastic potential of the nanotube, and electrostatic potential of the quantum dot. In reality, neither conversion process is completely reversible, and in each oscillation cycle some energy will be lost to both mechanical damping, and to resistance in the charging and discharging of the dot. Both dissipation mechanisms contribute to the overall quality factor of the system, defined as $Q = 2\pi \times \frac{\text{total energy}}{\text{energy dissipated per cycle}}$.

For oscillations outside the bias window, the change in the dot occupation is negligible. Therefore, we expect dissipation to result only from mechanical damping, and we should be able to measure a quality factor Q_{mech} associated solely with this mechanism. By comparing quality factor measurements inside and outside the bias window, we may therefore be able to infer the amount of energy dissipated in changing the dot occupation state – provided we also know how much energy is going into elastic and electrostatic potential respectively.

Consider the nanotube-dot system at maximum displacement, such that it is stationary with zero kinetic energy, and its total energy U_{tot} is given by the sum of elastic and electrostatic potential energy (which are both at their maximal values):

$$U_{\text{tot}} = V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}} + V_{\text{dot}}^{\text{max}}. \tag{73}$$

Over the course of one full mechanical oscillation cycle, the total energy dissipated by the system is given by a sum of contributions from the mechanical damping and dot resistance:

$$\Delta U_{\text{tot}} = \Delta U_{\text{mech}} + \Delta U_{\text{dot}}. \quad (74)$$

This allows us to express ΔU_{dot} in terms of the total and mechanical quality factors:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Q_{\text{tot}}}{2\pi} &= \frac{U_{\text{tot}}}{\Delta U_{\text{mech}} + \Delta U_{\text{dot}}} \\ \implies \Delta U_{\text{dot}} &= 2\pi \frac{U_{\text{tot}}}{Q_{\text{tot}}} - \Delta U_{\text{mech}} \\ &= 2\pi \left[\frac{U_{\text{tot}}}{Q_{\text{tot}}} - \frac{V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}}}{Q_{\text{mech}}} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

where $Q_{\text{mech}} = 2\pi \frac{V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}}}{\Delta U_{\text{mech}}}$. Assuming that the mechanical quality factor is independent of gate voltage, it should be possible to find Q_{mech} using the control protocol in Figure 4. It should also be possible to determine $V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}}$ from the measured amplitude z using the formula $V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}} = \frac{1}{2}m\omega_m^2 z^2$, where m is the estimated effective oscillating mass, and ω_m is the bare mechanical frequency.

On the other hand, $V_{\text{dot}}^{\text{max}}$ can be estimated using the method in Section 4, integrating $p(\mu(z))$ for the half cycle from minimum to maximum displacement. If $V_{\text{dot}}^{\text{max}} \ll V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}}$, then to a good approximation we can take $U_{\text{tot}} = V_{\text{mech}}^{\text{max}}$, simplifying Equation(75) to the following:

$$\Delta U_{\text{dot}} = \pi m \omega_m^2 z^2 \left[\frac{1}{Q_{\text{tot}}} - \frac{1}{Q_{\text{mech}}} \right]. \quad (76)$$

Note that the above expresses the energy dissipated while changing the dot occupation over a *whole* mechanical period (i.e., a charge and discharge cycle). We might assume that during the ‘erasure’ stroke, the dissipated energy is $\frac{1}{2}\Delta U_{\text{dot}}$.

7 Conclusion

We developed the experimental setup and theoretical model, and improved our understanding of the back-action of single-electron tunneling on mechanics, and vice versa. Incorporating an electrical cavity, we could provide a direct probe of the mechanical amplitude.

We extended the theoretical model from Ref.[2] to include energy-dependent tunnel barriers and the influence of electrostatic tensioning on the mechanical frequency. This allowed us to calculate how thermodynamic work can be estimated from the amplitude of mechanical oscillations, an experimentally accessible quantity.

With the objective of exploring thermodynamics at the nanoscale, taking inspiration from a piston coupled to a working fluid, this system presented exciting opportunities: the presence of Fermi reservoirs and the strong coupling of the quantum dot to these reservoirs lead to non-equilibrium conditions and quantum tunneling noise.

In examining the theory of erasure cost under these conditions, where thermal equilibrium cannot be assumed, we discovered that the work is related to the spread of the occupation distribution. This implies that the work cost depends on the probability of the electron being occupied or not. We determined that, depending on various conditions, the bound might be defined by the effective temperature (reducing to the original Landauer’s erasure), an energy scale defined by tunneling, or by the difference in electrochemical potentials. We conclude with the observation that connecting experimentally accessible and extractable quantities to fundamental bounds.

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Figure 5: **a)** Measured demodulated voltage V_{demod} as a function of gate voltage and driving frequency. For each gate voltage, the maximum indicates the effective mechanical resonance frequency. **b)** Amplitude of the mechanical oscillations Δz calculated from V_{meas} as described in Section 2.1. The dashed yellow line in (a) corresponds to $\omega_m(V_G)$ and the orange dash-dotted line to $\omega_{\text{eff}}(V_G)$ in the small amplitude limit (Equation (19)). Finally, the solid yellow curve is the effective mechanical frequency computed by integrating the equation of motion for an amplitude Δz corresponding to the maximum amplitude in (b) for each gate voltage.

Figure 6: Steady-state amplitude, (z/z_{zpm}) , of the driven CNT motion for different driving frequencies $f_{ex} = \frac{\omega_{ex}}{2\pi}$ and different chemical potentials μ_0 of the quantum dot (i.e., different gate voltages with $\Delta\mu_0 = -\alpha\Delta V_G$). Parameters: $T = 20$ mK, $\frac{\omega_m}{2\pi} = 289.5$ MHz, $m = 61$ ag, $Q_m = 10^4$, $V_{SD} = 2$ mV, $\frac{\gamma_S}{2\pi} = 1$ GHz, $\frac{\gamma_D}{2\pi} = 40$ GHz, $\frac{\gamma_m}{2\pi} = 800$ MHz, and drive amplitude $A_d = 30\omega_m\Gamma_m z_{zpm}$ (i.e., we expect an amplitude $\Delta z = 60z_{zpm}$ when driving at ω_m for a constant population).

Figure 7: **a)** Occupation is described by a function n of the dot's energy level μ , which is monotone-decreasing from 1 to 0. We're interested in the work cost of producing a definite state. In general, the cost of producing a state with $n = 0$ or $n = 1$ (denoted as W^0 and W^1 respectively) may differ, so we consider the average, $\bar{W} = \frac{1}{2}(W^0 + W^1)$. **b)** The work cost of erasure is determined by the *spread* of the occupation distribution. The derivative $n'(\mu) = -\frac{dn}{d\mu}$ defines a probability density function, and the work cost is related to its mean absolute deviation D by $\bar{W} = \frac{1}{2}D(n')$. For the Fermi-Dirac distribution (pictured), $\bar{W} = k_B T \ln 2$.

Figure 8: **a)** The steady-state occupation for a quantum dot in contact with two fermion reservoirs is described by a sum of Fermi-Dirac distributions weighted by the relative tunneling rates (pink dotted curve). Lifetime broadening has the effect of smoothing the occupation distribution (dark blue curve) by a function $g(\epsilon - \mu)$ which describes the spread of the dot's energy levels. Here, g is taken to be a Gaussian with standard deviation $\hbar\Gamma_{\text{broad}}$. **b)** The probability density function defined by the derivative of occupation has peaks at the source and drain chemical potentials. The width of each peak depends on the reservoir temperature and the lifetime broadening. The work cost of erasure \overline{W} is determined by the mean absolute deviation of the entire bimodal distribution, which depends on source-drain bias as well as the temperature and lifetime broadening.